

Content Management and Production Workflow System

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ABSTRACT

E-commerce has become integral part of our life, every one of us prefer online shopping than normal street shopping. Attractive offers, ample of varieties, heavy discount, easy return policies have promoted the E-commerce world to become so popular and will continue to dominate in near future also. The popularity of E-commerce website leads to the necessity of high levels of accuracy. Accuracy in terms of all the data which might be information about the product, display pictures of the product, its price, pattern and so on is expected by customers, so that they get the best shopping experience. But often it is found that while updating the website some data get interchange as a result it leads to bad user experience. Hence there is a necessity of the tool which will find error in content and help E-commerce website to display right data, leading to benefit both to customers as well as companies.

Keywords: *Quality Analysis, Production Workflow System, Angular JS, Firebase.*

1. INTRODUCTION

With growing technology, everything has come closer just at a distance of one click. Everything has come closer due to the world-wide web. Whenever we want something we go online and find the best stuff, satisfying our needs. Whenever we want to buy something, we prefer online shopping, since it provides ample of variety, heavy discount and also provide brands and latest stuffs. Everyday thousands of new stuffs are added to E-commerce website. E-commerce websites also allowed shopkeepers to sale their product online, leading to tremendous data both from individuals as well as from any company. But handling such huge data is not an easy task. Many times, it happens that data get interchange or data present is not appropriate as needed. At such time both customers as well as E-commerce website owner face problem. So, there is a need of a solution for this. So, our idea is to make a web portal where E-commerce website will provide data and this data will be analysed with the help of the tool and after proper analysis data is sent back to E-commerce websites for further process.

Earlier data analysis was done by a third party, by manually analysing the entire data, which was time-consuming and also chances of human errors prevails. Hence solution for this is this system which will eliminate the human error to great extent.

This application can be implemented using various technologies like HTML5, CSS3, AngularJS, Firebase, PHP and JavaScript. HTML5 is a mark-up language used for structuring and presenting content on the World Wide Web. JavaScript is a high level, dynamic, un typed, and interpreted programming language. It has been standardized in the ECMA Script language specification. Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) is a style sheet language used for describing the presentation of a document written in mark-up language. AngularJS (commonly referred to as "Angular") is an open-

source web application framework for developing single-page applications. Phone Gap is a mobile application development framework created by Nitobi (owned by Adobe Systems). It enables software programmers to build

applications for mobile devices using JavaScript, HTML5, and CSS3, instead of relying on platform-specific APIs like

those in iOS, Windows Phone, or Android. Fire-base is used for data-basing^[4].

2. REQUIREMENT ANALYSIS

The existing system is very time consuming and also error-prone. In the current system, some start-up companies like ReinLabs, get data from these E-commerce website, then they distribute this data with the help of email or pen drives then data are examined manually. This took almost a week, and chances of error still exist. Different solutions need to be defined and adopted in order to efficiently organize and manage large amount of data and processes to cope with them^[1]. Hence there is need to use latest technology to solve this problem. New technologies made it possible to solve all such issues. This can be done with the help of content management application. A content management application will allow content manager and author to manage the creation, modification and removal of content from activity operator's website. This means one can easily add content to a website without having to be a developer. A CMS may also provide tools for one-to-one marketing. This is the ability of the website to tailor its content and advertise to a visitor's specific characteristic. It does this by using information that is either provided the visitor themselves, or gathered by the website^[2]. With the help of new technology, new proposed system will be able to not only do simply the work of an employee, but also notify the client as well as employees about amount of work pending. A Client can even give a rating to different industries who are going to use this system. Which will promote the use of the new system.

3. SYSTEM ANALYSIS

In this new system, there will be separate login for clients, employees, project manager. Client will be able to upload the data and consequently he/she can specify the deadline or any other necessary needs of them. These data will go to the project manager who will assign the task to different employees as per the priority. Once Task is assigned employees can work on it and their work will be visible to project manager as well client, so

that the client will be assured that his/her work is under process. All of these task's handling will be done using Firebase server. All the data processing, login will be done through Firebase.

4. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

5. ADVANTAGES

- Unlike the manual system, this system is more flexible.
- The proposed system is easy to use and secure.
- It is convenient for client to upload data and to see work progress
- Project manager can assign task with help of portal itself
- A responsive screen which contain all detail of product will make employees work more easy

6. CONCLUSION

From the above study, we get much important knowledge about need of data analysis, so that appropriate data is uploaded on the website. E-commerce website are the need of today's world, everything and every variety are easily available on these websites, hence the need of its accuracy is must. When a customer surf on this website, they believe whatever data available is trustworthy, and make opinion over that data. Hence rectify the error will provide customers actual stuff which is available in markets and with actual pattern, colour and specification. Thus, both customers as well E-commerce website gets benefited. Often it found that client is not available to see the progress of that work, this system will solve this issues as well, whenever client will upload data for rectification he/she can see the progress of the data rectification work. In this way client, customers and our society all will get benefitted with this project.

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